

Exploring Surgical Interventions for Gastrointestinal and Hepato-Pancreato-Biliary Ascariasis

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Ascariasis is the most common helminthic disease in humans. It has global distribution and is most prevalent in tropical countries where the temperature and humidity favor the development of eggs in the soil. Ascaris is transmitted through fecal-oral route. Most of the affected are asymptomatic or present with nonspecific abdominal symptoms. However, because of the high prevalence of infection, complications can occur such as intestinal obstruction due to massive infestation, biliary colic, gallstone formation, cholecystitis, liver abscess recurrent pyogenic cholangitis and pancreatitis.

Material and Methods: Patients presented to the hospital with hepatopancreatobiliary and gastrointestinal ascariasis during the study period was included after taking due informed consent. A total of 100 adult patients were enrolled in the study. A detailed clinical history was taken from all the patients. Ultrasonography of whole abdomen was done in all patients. X-ray abdomen in erect and/or supine posture was done in patients presenting with features of intestinal obstruction. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was done in some patients.

Results: The patterns of diseases could be classified into 4 broad categories namely: biliary colic, acute pancreatitis, acute cholangitis and intestinal obstruction. Ninety percent of patients (90/100) could be managed successfully conservatively. Endoscopic removal of worms from biliary tract was done successfully in 6 patients. 4 patients underwent surgery for unrelenting cholangitis due to dead worms in the common bile duct.

Conclusion: Gastrointestinal and hepatopancreatobiliary ascariasis has a high disease burden in study area. The disease reflects sanitation habits of the population and has a wide spectrum of manifestations. Management is predominantly conservative and the prognosis good. Sanitary habits should be advised and the family dewormed if an index case of ascariasis is found in the population.

Keywords: Acute Pancreatitis, Ascariasis, Biliary, Upper Gastrointestinal Endoscopy.

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Introduction

Ascariasis in human beings is a well-known condition with most common presentation being the intestinal Ascariasis (IA). The incidence of intestinal Ascariasis is high in children compared to adults. The hepatobiliary Ascariasis (HBA) and pancreatic Ascariasis (PA) are the known complications of Ascariasis especially in endemic regions due to high prevalence of the infection. The disease is most prevalent in tropical and subtropical developing countries. [1-3] though it is an intestinal parasite, the worm can migrate to extraintestinal organs like the biliary system with an occasional invasion of the biliary tract leading to a variety of complications including cholecystitis, obstructive jaundice, and cholangitis. [4] Hepatobiliary and pancreatic ascariasis are being diagnosed more often recently, with the development of diagnostic imaging techniques (ultrasound, computed tomography scan, etc.) Diagnosis of biliary Ascaris by ultrasound examination of the abdomen can show a mobile

worm with an echogenic wall and central hypoechogenicity in the bile ducts and gall bladder with a sensitivity of up to 86% [5] Acute cholangitis is a hepatobiliary tract infection, with high mortality, unless treated early. Urgent biliary decompression is essential to reduce the elevated intra-biliary pressure and improve clinical outcome. [6] Ascaris obstruction is a rare etiology of cholangitis. Patients may be asymptomatic or present with biliary colic, cholangitis, cholecystitis, liver abscess, pancreatitis, intestinal obstruction and even perforation. [7] PA is the presence of worms in the pancreatic/biliary ducts resulting in pancreatitis. The objective of this study was to record the various clinical profiles and management protocols being followed for patients with gastrointestinal and hepatobiliary ascariasis admitted in a tertiary care center of India.

Material and Methods

This observational study was conducted at Department of General Surgery Tertiary Care Teaching Institute of India for the duration of 1 year. Patients presented to the hospital with hepatopancreatobiliary and gastrointestinal ascariasis during the study period was included after taking due informed consent. Unwilling patients were not included in the study. Ethical clearance was obtained from Institute Ethics Committee. A total of 100 adult patients were enrolled in the study. A detailed clinical history was taken from all the patients. Routine laboratory workup included blood counts, coagulation profile, liver function tests, serum amylase, lipase and stool for ova and cyst of parasites. Ultrasonography of whole abdomen was done in all patients. X-ray abdomen in erect and/or supine posture was done in patients presenting with features of intestinal obstruction. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was done in some patients. Patients were managed conservatively initially and surgical intervention was done in those patients who did not respond after 48-72 hours of conservative management.

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA).

Quantitative variables were described as means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range based on their distribution. Qualitative variables were presented as count and percentages. For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results

A total of 100 patients were included in the study-78 females and 22 males. Age of the patients ranged from 17 years to 72 years with a mean of 34.10 years and majority of patients below 30 years age. The patterns of diseases could be classified into 4 broad categories namely: biliary colic, acute pancreatitis, acute cholangitis and intestinal obstruction. The symptomatology is summarised in Table 1 and frequency of various diagnoses in study population is summarized in Table 2. The yield of various investigative modalities is summarised in Table 3.

No patient had undergone any biliary tract intervention prior to current admission. Ninety percent of patients (90/100) could be managed successfully conservatively. Endoscopic removal of worms from biliary tract was done successfully in 6 patients. 4 patients underwent surgery for unrelenting cholangitis due to dead worms in the common bile duct. None of the patients presenting with sub-acute intestinal obstruction needed surgical intervention and were managed successfully with conservative management.

Table 1: Clinical features of the study population

Clinical feature	Number	Percentage (%)
Pain abdomen	100	100
Vomiting	72	72
Fever	25	25
Jaundice	26	26
Altered bowel habits (constipation)	17	17
History of passing worms in stool	10	10
History of vomiting worms	7	7

Table 2: Diagnosis with frequency in the study population.

Diagnosis	Number	Percentage (%)
Biliary colic	40	40
Worm induced acute pancreatitis	33	33
Cholangitis	20	20
Sub-acute intestinal obstruction	7	7

Table 3: Diagnostic and ancillary investigations with the yield from each investigation

Investigations	No. of patients (n=100)	Suggestive of ascariasis	Percentage (%)
Ultrasonography	100	96	96
Stool ova-cyst	100	90	90
Upper GI endoscopy	10	6	6
Raised serum amylase/lipase	100	33	33
X-ray abdomen	20	4	20

Discussion

Ascariasis is the commonest helminthic infection in humans caused by a Nematode *Ascaris lumbricoides*. Ascariasis is common in regions

where poor sanitation, overcrowding and poverty favors the feco-oral spread of the parasite. Worm infestation is caused by ingestion of eggs from contaminated soil, food or water. The larvae emerge

in the duodenum; migrate to the caecum, the veins of portal system and to the liver. From the hepatic veins they migrate to the lungs and heart. Transport to the lungs can also occur through the lymphatics of the bowel and the thoracic duct. After entering into the tracheobronchial tree, the larvae are swallowed. Mature worms develop in the small intestine and eggs are passed in the feces. The adult worm resides in the duodenum and distal ileum. [8]

The disease can have different presentations, depending on the organs and systems affected. The spectrum of clinical diseases includes pulmonary, intestinal (including intestinal obstruction), appendicular, hepatobiliary, and pancreatic ascariasis.

The Hepatobiliary Ascariasis (HBA) and pancreatic Ascariasis (PA) includes group of diseases caused by migration of adult worm through ampulla of Vater into biliary and pancreatic ducts. The invasion of the worm into the pancreatic duct is rare due to the small caliber of the duct. [9-11] although worms appear to migrate through ampulla into biliary tree and pancreatic ducts most appear to return spontaneously to the intestine within 72 hrs of inducing biliary symptoms. Hence hepatobiliary and pancreatic Ascariasis escapes detection unless diagnostic imaging was performed during active clinical disease. HBA and PA can occur in any age group, the maximum incidence occurs in the third and fourth decade. HBA and PA are less prevalent in children due to narrow orifices. They are predominantly the diseases of the women with women to men ratio of 3:1. Pregnancy predisposes women to HBA and PA. In addition, interventional procedures related to biliary tract are also risk factors for HBA and PA. [12,13,14] high incidence of pancreatitis was noted in the present study similar to the findings by Khuroo et al. [8] However Mukhopadhyaya and Khuroo et al reported a very low incidence of acute pancreatitis in their patients in other parts of Indian subcontinent. [8,15] A female predominance was seen in the present study similar to findings by Mukhopadhyay. [8] A high sensitivity has been observed for ultrasonography in diagnosing biliary tree ascariasis 98.84% in the present study similar to the findings by Das. [10]

The spectrum of clinical diseases includes pulmonary, intestinal (including intestinal obstruction), appendicular, hepatobiliary, and pancreatic ascariasis. [12] Some factors increase the possibility of HBA: a prior history of hepatobiliary surgery. Pregnancy, the environment surrounding the worm; for instance, fever, prolonged fasting, etc. [8,16] In our patient, even though he has a risk factor to develop ascariasis, no risk factor has been identified that predisposes him for HBA.

Conservative management was successful in 90% of patients similar to previous studies. [8,9]

Conservative treatment included antispasmodics, antibiotics and antihelminthics. Other medications including pyrantel pamoate, levamisole, piperazine citrate and thiabendazole can be used as well with an efficacy of 90–100%. [14]

Ideally, a stool sample should be repeated 2 weeks after starting the medication to confirm successful treatment. In biliary ascariasis, anti-helminth should be delayed until the worms spontaneously exit the biliary tree or addressed by endoscopy/surgery. This is because, if treatment is given while the worm is still present in the biliary tree, its death and subsequent carcass can lead to further complications. When conservative treatment fails endoscopic or open surgical management is indicated. ERCP for biliary drainage and decompression is the treatment of choice in biliary ascariasis.

A significant reduction in morbidity and mortality of hepatobiliary ascariasis has been noted since the introduction of endoscopic intervention. [17,18] Worms were removed from ampulla of Vater using endoscopic snares in 6 patients in the present series which hastened the recoveries of the patients. ERCP has been used successfully in removing worm's especially dead worms from the biliary tree. [19] In the present series ERCP was not done as the facility was not available in the Hospital, and the dead worms had to be removed surgically. Less than 1% of patients require surgical interventions, especially when endoscopic interventions were not able to extract dead worms. [20]

USG is the primary modality in the evaluation of abdominal pain and other abdominal symptoms. Hence prior information of the features of ascariasis especially the three sonographic signs, along with the characteristic movement of the worm within the bowel lumen are very important clues for the diagnosis of the Ascariasis. Even though these features and signs are described first based on the USG appearance of the worm in previous studies, CECT revealed similar appearance in the hepatobiliary system and intestine with better demonstration of cholangitis and liver abscess.

Conclusion

Gastrointestinal and hepatopancreatobiliary ascariasis has a high disease burden in study area. The disease reflects sanitation habits of the population and has a wide spectrum of manifestations. The diagnosis is based on clinical suspicion and imaging. Stool examination is of corroborative value in diagnosis. Management is predominantly conservative and the prognosis good. Sanitary habits should be advised and the family dewormed if an index case of ascariasis is found in the population. Particularly the primary care physicians can play a big role in this endeavour.

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